

MONITORING THE PULTRUSION PROCESS TO ASSURE CONSTANT QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

Pultrusion is a manufacturing process that produces fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) profiles or semi-finished products continuously. The basic problem with the process monitoring for thermoset pultrusion are the complex reactions in the die. Until now the monitoring of the reaction conditions can not be done sufficiently by the external process parameters (pulling force, die temperature). To transduce information of the reactions in the die, in principle three different sensors are available: Thermo elements, dielectrical- and pressure sensors. The paper shows the results of temperature, die-pressure and conductance measurements in dependence of different production parameters. It can be shown, that the conductivity is a direct value for the reaction in the die (viscosity of the resin). The course of the conductivity is influenced by all major external parameters (pulling-speed, resin, die-temperature, fibre/volume contents, additives). The results of mechanical tests prove the monitored effects of the process parameters on the mechanical properties. The combination of pressure- and conductivity data on the one side and pulling force and die-temperature on the other enables modern pultruders to manufacture assured constant quality.

Keywords: Pultrusion, quality assurance, conductance, die pressure

1. THE PULTRUSION PROCESS

Pultrusion is a production process for composites which is specifically suitable for the large scale production of endless fibre reinforced profiles or semi finished products. Compared with other manufacturing processes for composites, pultrusion is known since 1951. Today pultruded profiles have found their small but rapidly growing market with all kinds of applications all over the world. The growing number of applications for pultruded profiles leads to numerous new profiles of all shapes and sizes (figure 1). /1/

Besides various standard geometries like L, U, O and flat hollow and full profiles many custom made geometries have been developed. The use of several cores for the production of multi

chamber profiles is standard today. The profile size can vary between a few square millimeters for cable elements and many square meters for cover panels of bridges.

Figure 1: Pultruded profiles

1.1. Fibres and matrix

The pultrusion process allows the processing of many fibres and low viscosity matrix systems. Figure 2 shows a summary of the fibre matrix combinations used today. The different matrices can be divided into thermoset and thermoplastic systems. Whereas the traditional polyester resins, epoxy, vinylster and phenolic systems are used in large scale production industrially, thermoplastic matrix systems are still in the phase of prototype production only.

<u>matrix</u>		<u>fibre</u>	
thermoset:	polyester (up)	glas:	ud-roving
	vinylester (ve)		spinnroving
	epoxy (ep)		matt
	vail		
reactive:	polyamide (pa)		fabric
thermoplastic:	polyamide (pa)	carbon:	ud-roving
	polypropylene (pp)		fabric
	polyester (pet/pbt)	aramid:	ud-roving
	polyurethan (pu)		fabric
	polyethersulfon (pes)		
	polyetherketone (peek)		

Figure 2: Fibre and matrix material used for pultrusion

1.2. The pultrusion machine

Figure 3 shows a horizontally working standard pultrusion machine as it is used for industrial production today. These standard pultrusion machines are approximately 20 to 30 meters long with an extreme width of 1,5 meters.

Figure 3: Standard horizontal pultrusion mashine

With reference to figure 3 the first machine part in the direction of production is the coil magazine followed by the impregnation station. Here the matrix, in general a thermoset-system, is applied to the dry and sometimes preheated fibres. In the following die the impregnated rovings and vails are formed, calibrated and heated. The introduced thermal energy causes the polymerisation process and the curing of the thermoset matrix within the die. During the long distance between the die and the pulling device the profile will end the curing of the matrix and cool down. This enables the clamps of the pulling mechanism to grip the profile sufficiently and pull the profile through the process. Finally a synchronized saw cuts the profiles to length /2/.

1.3. Process steps and their settings

The eight different process steps are characterized with the variable process settings within the step. These variable process settings can be adjusted directly at the machine (e.g. die temperature, pulling speed). The real process parameters like temperature, stress in the profile and the viscosity of the matrix can not be set directly.

It is clear that all the process settings influence the product quality. This includes mechanical and optical properties. These properties are influenced within the three major areas of impregnation, moulding and curing. It is obvious, that same settings influence the internal process within more than one area. For example the pulling speed influences the process in all three major areas. Due to these numerous interactions, until now it has not been possible to set up a sufficient process model to describe the product qualities with the process settings.

2. MONITORING THE PULTRUSION PROCESS

The previous chapters showed basically that the monitoring of the pultrusion process with thermoset matrix systems is changed by the hidden reaction process within the die. Again, due to the numerous interactions of the process parameters even only the polymerisation-reaction in the die is hard to predict. Basically three different kinds of sensors are available to monitor the reaction within the die:

1. Temperature,
2. Pressure and
3. Dielectrical sensors

The first problem to be solved is however the adaptation of the known sensor technology to the pultrusion process with its severe abrasion problem. In the following chapters this paper will show the sensors used and the results of the recorded data in dependance of various process parameter settings like die temperature, fibre volume contents and pulling speed.

2.1. Sensors

Figure 4: Bores for the pressure and dielectrical sensors

The trial temperature is monitored with thin thermocouples which are run through the die with the fibres. Furtheron usual temperature elements are placed in the die close to the inner surface. The pressure sensors are placed at the beginning and in the middle of the pultrusion die (die length 1000mm).

The surface of these strain gauge pressure sensors /3/ are chrome plated to withstand the abrasive glas fibres. Figure 4 shows the blue prints of the bores which take the pressure sensor and the stationary dielectrical sensor. The IKV dielectrical sensor is designed to match usual pressure sensor bores /4/.

Figure 5: Ceramic and film sensor for conductivity measurement

The fotos in figure 5 show the two different dielectrical sensors used. Next to the already metioned stationary sensor (left picture: ceramic sensor) a film sensor /5/ (Idex-sensor) is used. This film sensor is pulled through the die with the fibres and remains in the profile after curing. Therefore this sensor can only be used once and is not always suitable for industrial production monitoring.

2.2. Measuring the conductivity

Figure 6: Cross section of die with electrical field

Basically the main principle of the dielectrical sensor is that of a two-plate condenser with the polymer as the dielectric material. An alternating current applied will cause the molecules to move. Dependend on the current frequency, the molecule size (grade of polymerisation) and viscosity of the material the conductivity changes. This means that generally the lower the viscosity of the material is, the higher is the conductivity resp. a lower resistance.

The stationary ceramic sensor is equipped with one part of the two-plate condenser, the other is the die itself. Figure 6 shows principally the electrical field lines of this sensor type. The Idex film sensor however is equipped with both sides of the two-plate condenser. They are placed side by side in the form of fine printed circuits. Therefore the conductivity of the two sensor types can not be compared directly. More information

on the dielectrical measurement technologie for FRP can be found e.g. in /6/.

3. PULTRUSION TRIALS: RESULTS

The first investigations in the field of process monitoring with the pultrusion process deal with the influence of die temperature, fibre contents and pulling speed on the die pressure and conductivity.

3.1. Film sensor and temperature results

Figure 7: Conductance and temperature course over the die length, $v = 140^\circ \text{C}$, $v = 50 \text{ cm/min}$, $\rho = 78\%$

Figure 8: Conductance and temperature course over the die length, $v = 160^\circ \text{C}$, $v = 50 \text{ cm/min}$, $\rho = 78\%$

Figure 9: Conductance and temperature course over the die length, $v = 140^\circ \text{C}$, $v = 25 \text{ cm/min}$, $\rho = 78\%$

The figures 7 to 9 show the conductivity and temperature course within the die for three different pultrusion settings. The courses are monitored with the help of the Idex film sensor. The temperature was followed by thermo couples. The comparison of the three conductance curves demonstrates the dependance of the conductivity course due to change of parameter settings (figure 10). Especially for specific points within the die a significant change of conductivity can be observed.

Figure 10: Comparison of conductivity course of different settings

This means for the use of build in sensors in the die, that changes of reaction can be monitored. It is proved by the results of the trials with the ceramic sensor in the following chapter.

3.2. Build in ceramic dielectrical sensor

Figure 11 summarizes the course of the stationary dielectrical sensor in dependance of the temperature. Here the conductivity is printed over the pultrusion time. It can be seen that changes of die temperature and therefore reaction cinetics and with that the resin viscosity lead to a rise in conductance. Another parameter to influence the reaction cinetics and the resin viscosity is the pultrusion speed. The trial results are summerized in figure 12. As slow pulling speeds and higher die temperatures both lead to an increase in reactivity, they both show the higher values of conductivity.

Figure 11: Conductance in dependance of pultrusion time and die temperature

Figure 12: Conductance in dependance of pultrusion time and pulling speed

Figure 13. reaction of conductivity value on introduction of additional roving

Because of its significance for pultrusion process quality assurance in industry, especially the fibre volume contents influence on the conductivity is demonstrated in another experiment. Where as changes of die temperature can be monitored easily by the die control unit, brakage of single rovings can not be detected without great efforts.

The following figure (figure 13) shows the conductivity response on an additionally introduced roving -vice versa to the brakage of one fibre. The very clear change of conductance is precise evidence of the different fibre contents. Therefore this value can be used to monitor the main parameters of the pultrusion process in one.

3.3 Results of the pressure measurements

The two pressures measured -at the beginning of the die and in the middle- show comparable results for these trials with glas and polyester matrix. The figures 14 and 15 show the dependance of the pressure from the pulling speed, die temperature and fibre volume contents:

Figure 16: Die pressure in dependance of die temperature and pulling speed, $\rho = 83\%$

Figure 17: Die pressure in dependance of fibre contents and pulling speed, $v = 140^\circ\text{C}$

The demonstrated results show that the pressure sensors too, allow a sufficient monitoring of the process in the die. Furtheron the die pressure (upon others) is responsible for the quality of the profile surface. However the sensor technology for pressure measurement for pultrusion applications is far more complicated to handle than the simple, flat dielectrical sensor.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The shown results demonstrate that the existing sensors -pressure and conductance- supply sufficient data to ensure and record a ensure and reproducable production of profiles. Especially the recording of production data will become more and more necessary to proove the quality of the product. In combination with statistical samples for mechanical tests, machine parameters like pulling speed, die temperature and the mentioned sensor data the first step into a closed quality control is set.

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